

用于监测研发发展优先领域的研究和信息工具

**RESEARCH AND INFORMATION TOOLS FOR MONITORING
PRIORITY AREAS FOR R&D DEVELOPMENT**

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抽象的。 本文提出了一种解决开发研究和信息工具以监测研发发展优先领域的问题的方法。 这篇文章证实了使用“漏斗”方法选择资源和创新想法的便利性, 以及用于监测它们的研究和信息工具。

关键词: 监测、研发发展、优先领域、效率、研究和信息工具。

Abstract. *The article presents an approach to solving the problem of developing research and information tools for monitoring priority areas of R&D development. The article substantiates the expediency of using the “funnel” method for selecting resources and innovative ideas, as well as research and information tools for their monitoring.*

Keywords: *monitoring, R&D development, priority areas, efficiency, research and information tools.*

Introduction

Significant limitation of competition of domestic manufacturing enterprises and their artificial exclusion from the chains of globalization of the world economy poses a number of new tasks for them. One of the most important among them is to increase the scientific justification and monitoring of the effectiveness of activities carried out as part of the development of priority areas of research and development (R&D). Development of marketing information and analytical tools is the reason of increasing the effectiveness of such events. Such tools make it possible to most objectively evaluate the results obtained in the course of indi-

vidual R&D, conduct their comparative analysis, and also determine the contribution of research and development and other organizations to their implementation. However, currently existing methods do not have such capabilities, since they use mainly subjective quantitative characteristics and their weighting coefficients for monitoring purposes.

New market requirements form the prerequisites not only for the emergence of innovations, but also for a significant increase in their localization. In this regard, it is necessary to improve methods of managing the creation of innovative products (services, technologies). The introduction of such methods in the market will expand the range of offers of new products and services, as well as provide consumer demand for them from various groups of the population and other enterprises. In this regard, it seems relevant to adapt existing and develop new methods for monitoring the effectiveness of the implementation of activities in the framework of the development of priority R&D areas. Their practical application will entail the emergence of a synergistic effect due to a more rational use of available resources, expanding the practice of using modern innovative mechanisms and information and analytical tools to monitor the implementation of activities.

Main part

For the practical realization of these activities, it is necessary: to develop mechanisms for transferring the innovative potential and resources that the region has into innovative products (services, technologies); develop mechanisms for bringing these products to the market; develop and implement new marketing mechanisms for generating demand for innovative products (services, technologies) and their promotion to the market [1].

The selection of resources for their transfer into innovative products (services, technologies) is advisable to use the “funnel” method. Its essence lies in the sequential execution of the following operations.

1. Selection of resources for creating new products (services, technologies).
2. Evaluation of the possibility of obtaining these resources.
3. Generating a new business idea.
4. Testing the idea of creating new products (services, technologies).
5. Initial selection of an idea for its practical implementation.
6. Formulation of the idea in the form of an innovative project.
7. Determining the conditions for the implementation of the project.
8. Development of a prototype of new products (services, technologies).
9. Entry of innovative products (services, technologies) to the market.
10. Further improvement and introduction of innovative products (services, technologies) to new markets [2].

The mechanism of this method is based on the conditional allocation of the entire set of resources, their selection from the point of view of the prospects

for creating new products (services, technologies), the further generation of ideas for creating new products (services, technologies), the selection of potentially promising ideas, the choice of a specific idea. Taking into account the above circumstances, the selection of innovative products (services, technologies) for their subsequent implementation should be based on the determination of a number of criteria values for the effectiveness of this process, depending on various groups of potential users: the state, the population, business structures, etc. Usually determined: target efficiency, economic efficiency, socio-economic efficiency and number of other indicators [3].

For the initial assessment of innovative ideas, we can use the tools to stimulate innovation and the methodology for its practical implementation. The main purpose of the technique is the ability to relatively quickly assess the prospects of an innovative idea with a small expenditure of resources, which will make it possible to make an informed choice among alternative options for its implementation.

It seems appropriate to use the following areas of assessment:

1. Market opportunities - an assessment of its size, development dynamics, the presence of barriers to entry into the market, the degree of competition intensity, the value of the market rate of return.
2. Business opportunities - assessment of the correspondence of an idea with the experience and capabilities of enterprises in the region.
3. Justification of the idea - assessment of the level of attractiveness and complexity of the implementation of the idea.
4. Availability and accessibility of resources - assessment of the availability of existing and the necessity to attract additional resources to implement the idea.
5. User capabilities - assessment of the price and production characteristics of an idea (product, service), what consumer problems and how the idea solves, does it have unique properties.
6. Opportunities for patenting an idea – assessment of the necessity for patent or other protection of an idea.

The assessment methodology implemented in practice through the formation of appropriate tables for each area of assessment. Each indicator presented in the tables (matrices) evaluated on a 10-point scale (from the minimum score (-5 points) to the maximum score (+5 points)). Then the scores summed up: first for each table separately, and then for all tables together.

The final values obtained as a result of summation characterize the expert assessment of the degree of riskiness (probability) of the implementation of the idea. To obtain more accurate estimates and improve the validity of the final results, we can implement weighting coefficients that take into account the importance of a particular indicator for a particular area of innovation activity.

When comparing alternative ideas, it is necessary to approach their evaluation with the same criteria. The algorithm for implementing the methodology provides for the sequential execution of the following steps:

Stage 1. Business idea formulation, brief description.

Stage 2. Evaluation of the idea in the proposed areas using tables 1–6.

Stage 3. Summing up the assessment. Summing up is carried out by filling in the table below 7.

Stage 4. Evaluation of the prospects for the implementation of the idea as part of the implementation of this stage, we can make a conclusion about the prospects for the implementation of the generated idea. If there are good prospects, it is possible to admit the idea for further consideration for its implementation as an innovative entrepreneurial project.

Table 1
Direction «Market Opportunities»

Negative indicators			Positive indicators		
-5	-2,5	0	0	+2,5	+5
The market is too small to develop an idea			The market has good prospects for the development of the idea		
Potential market is static or tends to shrink			Potential market sector is in the growth stage		
Entry to the market is limited by serious barriers			Entering the market will be relatively easy		
Market leaders are large firms with unlimited resources			Competitors in the market are weak and will not be able to organize a rebuff to the emergence of a new structure		
There is fierce competition in the market, which reduces profit margins			Profit margin in the market is attractive and not limited by competition		

Table 2
Direction «Business Opportunities»

Negative indicators			Positive indicators		
-5	-2,5	0	0	+2,5	+5
The implementation of the idea will entail the diversification of the company's product range			The idea lies in line with the mission of innovative development of the company		
The idea will require the development of a new client base			The implementation of the idea focused on the existing customer base		
The implementation of the idea will require the involvement of new knowledge and qualified personnel.			The implementation of the idea will not require the involvement of new knowledge and qualified personnel		

Operational phase will require investment in production and/or distribution systems	Existing production and distribution system will not require investment during the operation phase
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Table 3
Direction “Substantiation of the idea”

Negative indicators			Positive indicators		
-5	-2,5	0	0	+2,5	+5
The implementation of the idea based on new principles and concepts			The implementation of the idea based on proven principles and concepts		
The implementation of the idea implies the creation of a new product concept			Implementation of an idea is a new application of a product or process		
The successful implementation of an idea depends on the results of other developments			The successful implementation of an idea does not depend on the results of other developments		
The successful implementation of the idea requires the integration of several complex systems			The successful implementation of the idea does not require the integration of complex systems		
Additional permits and approvals required for the successful implementation of the idea			Successful implementation of the idea does not depend on additional permits and approvals		

Table 4
Direction “Availability and accessibility of resources”

Negative indicators			Positive indicators		
-5	-2,5	0	0	+2,5	+5
Successful implementation of the idea requires a significant number of additional resources			Successful implementation of the idea does not require a significant number of additional resources		
Developing and implementing of the idea will take a lot of time			The development and implementation of the idea will not take much time		
The development and implementation of the idea largely depends on external funding			We have our own resources to develop and implement the idea		
Additional specialists required to develop and implement the idea			No additional specialists required to develop and implement the idea		

Table 5
Direction «User capabilities»

Negative indicators			Positive indicators		
-5	-2,5	0	0	+2,5	+5
The implementation of the idea does not provide any additional benefits for users			The implementation of the idea will provide unique benefits for users		
The implementation of the idea will not improve the performance of the product			The implementation of the idea will improve the performance of the product		
The new product will not have a price advantage			The cost advantages of the new product will be significant		
The implementation of the idea will require special efforts to reduce the negative impact on the environment			The implementation of the idea will not have a negative impact on the environment		
The benefits of implementing the idea will not be appreciated by users			From the implementation of the idea, users will receive great convenience and satisfaction of their needs		

Table 6
Direction “Opportunities for patenting an idea”

Negative indicators			Positive indicators		
-5	-2,5	0	0	+2,5	+5
Other firms can easily copy the idea			It will be difficult for other firms to copy the idea		
The prospects for effective patent protection of the idea are very weak			An idea can be protected by registration, patenting, etc.		
Income from licensing will not cover the costs of developing and implementing the idea			It is possible to receive additional income through licensing agreements with other firms		

Table 7
Final assessment of the possibility of implementing the idea

Direction of evaluation	1	2	3	4	5	6	TOTAL
Points							

Otherwise, the methodology allows the possibility of combining new parameters for the implementation of the idea under consideration or the development of new ideas, where various combinations of existing and new factors, characteristics, variables and other components will be used as parameters.

Conclusion

As a result of the practical use of the “funnel” method and described above research and information tools and the methodology for selecting innovative ideas,

we can monitor priority areas for the development of R&D. This can help to make a more informed choice of ideas for creating innovative products, technologies, services and their subsequent implementation as part of the development of priority R&D areas.

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